

DFG ABSCHLUSSBERICHT

The use of comparative phylogeographic and ecologic modeling to disentangle interacting evolutionary processes in contrasting clades: the example of Malagasy mouse lemurs (*Microcebus*), sportive lemurs (*Lepilemur*) and woolly lemurs (*Avahi*)

by Prof. Dr. Ute Radespiel

Figure 1: **A:** Sampling localities and taxonomic assignments (*Microcebus* spp.) which were used for and derived from this project (van Elst et al. 2025a); **B:** Study sites in focal region with species occurrences (Schüßler et al. 2025a, supplemented with unpublished data). Newly surveyed sites are marked with an asterisk. The blue numbers indicate the inter-river-systems (IRSs) of the region, and names of some relevant, larger rivers are provided. Elevation, rivers and protected areas are also illustrated.

ABSCHLUSSBERICHT/FINAL REPORT

1 Allgemeine Angaben/General information

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Titel des Projekts/Title of project:

(1) The use of comparative phylogeographic and ecologic modeling to disentangle interacting evolutionary processes in contrasting clades: the example of Malagasy mouse lemurs (*Microcebus*), sportive lemurs (*Lepilemur*) and woolly lemurs (*Avahi*);
in the prolongation proposal:

(2) The use of comparative phylogeographic and ecologic modelling to disentangle interacting evolutionary processes in contrasting clades: the example of Malagasy mouse lemurs (*Microcebus*) and woolly lemurs (*Avahi*)

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2 Zusammenfassung / Summary

Artbildungsprozesse sind divers und komplex. Sie können durch topographische Barrieren aber auch durch ökologische Mechanismen beeinflusst werden, z.B. die Flexibilität von Arten in der Habitatwahl oder durch unterschiedliche Beweglichkeit zwischen Habitaten. Die meisten bisherigen Studien untersuchten gleichzeitig nur die Rolle von wenigen Faktoren bei der Artentstehung. Wir untersuchten den Einfluss mehrerer wichtiger Faktoren auf die Diversifizierung von nachtaktiven Lemuren, vorwiegend in Ost-Madagaskar. Zwei Gattungen, die kleinen, artenreichen Mausmakis (*Microcebus* spp.: 7 Arten) und die mittelgroßen Wollmakis (*Avahi* spp.: 2 Arten) wurden als Modelle ausgewählt. Eine andere Gattung (Wieselmakis, *Lepilemur* spp.) war leider bereits zu selten, um sie in die Analysen einbeziehen zu können. Dieses Projekt hatte zum Ziel, den relativen Einfluss von topographischen Barrieren (Flüsse, Höhenlagen), Körpergröße, ökologischer Flexibilität, Anpassungsfähigkeit an menschliche Habitatveränderungen, sowie des artspezifischen Wanderungsvermögens auf die Verbreitungsmuster der Lemuren zu untersuchen. Es waren Rückschlüsse möglich auf die Diversifizierung über verschiedene räumlich-zeitliche Skalen (von der Population bis zur Art). Wir haben im Projekt insgesamt 22 Studiengebiete in 15 Inter-Fluss-Systemen in Nordost-Madagaskar besucht und je eine Probe von 286 Mausmakis und 35 Wollmakis genommen für genomische Analysen. Sowohl Flüsse als auch Höhenlagen stellen bei Mausmakis Barrieren für Genfluss dar, obwohl diese Effekte nicht für alle Arten gleich sind, sondern verschiedene Arten offenbar unterschiedlich flexibel sind und sich ihre Wanderungsfähigkeit unterscheidet. *Microcebus lehilahytsara* besitzt z.B. trotz seiner kleinsten Körpergröße das größte Verbreitungsgebiet aller Vergleichsarten, eine hohe ökologische Flexibilität, hohe Migrationsraten gerade

auch über das Hochland, und kam sowohl in Hochlandwäldern fast aller Inter-Fluss-Systeme als auch in einigen Tieflandwäldern vor, dort teilweise gemeinsam anderen Mausmaki-Arten. Im Gegensatz dazu kam *M. macarthurii* nur in einem Inter-Fluss-System vor und ist offenbar nicht zur Abwanderung über die Quellgebiete der begrenzenden Flüsse in der Lage. Mittelhohe Wanderungsfähigkeit und eine regionale Verbreitung konnte hingegen für *M. jonahi* und *M. simmonsii* festgestellt werden, die gepaart war mit mittlerer bzw. begrenzter ökologischer Flexibilität. Ähnlich komplexe Diversifizierungsmuster wurden parallel in zwei anderen Studien einmal lokal für *M. gerpi* und einmal inselweit für alle Mausmaki-Arten im Rahmen dieses Projekts festgestellt. Die mittelgroßen *A. laniger* zeigten erwartungsgemäß eine hohe Migrationsfähigkeit, obwohl ein bestimmter Fluss für sie aber nicht für *M. lehilahytsara* eine Barriere darstellte. Daher lässt sich das artspezifische Ausbreitungsvermögen nicht klar durch Unterschiede in der Körpergröße, sondern eher durch Unterschiede in der ökologischen Flexibilität der Arten erklären.

Species formation processes are diverse and complex. They can be influenced by topographical barriers but also by ecological mechanisms, e.g. differential flexibility in habitat selection or different mobility between habitats. Most previous studies have analysed the simultaneous role of only a few factors for the evolution of species. We investigated the simultaneous influence of several important factors on the diversification of nocturnal lemurs, mainly in eastern Madagascar. Two genera, the small, species-rich mouse lemurs (*Microcebus* spp.: 7 species) and the medium-sized woolly lemurs (*Avahi* spp.: 2 species) were selected as models. Another genus (weasel lemurs, *Lepilemur* spp.) was already too rare to be included in the analyses. The aim of this project was to investigate the relative influence of topographic barriers (rivers, elevation), body size, ecological flexibility, adaptability to human habitat changes and species-specific migratory ability on the distribution patterns of lemurs. We were able to draw conclusions about diversification at different spatio-temporal scales (from population to species). We visited a total of 22 study sites in 15 inter-river systems in northeast Madagascar for this project and sampled 286 mouse lemurs and 35 woolly lemurs for genomic analyses. Both rivers and elevation act as barriers to gene flow for mouse lemurs, but these effects are evenly expressed for all species. Indeed, different species appear to possess different ecological flexibility and migratory abilities. Despite its smallest body size, *Microcebus lehilahytsara* had the largest distribution of all species, a high ecological flexibility, high migration rates especially across the highlands, and was found in highland forests of almost all inter-river systems as well as in some lowland forests, sometimes together with other mouse lemur species. On the other end of the spectrum, *M. macarthurii* only occurred in one inter-river system and is apparently unable to migrate across the headwaters of the two bordering rivers. *Microcebus jonahi* and *M. simmonsii* each had intermediate migratory abilities and a regional distribution, which was paired with medium or limited ecological flexibility, respectively. Similarly complex diversification patterns were found in parallel in two other studies within this project, one on *M. gerpi* and one on all mouse lemur species on the island. In contrast, the medium-sized *A. laniger* showed a high migratory ability as expected, although one river was a barrier for this species but not for the small *M. lehilahytsara*. Therefore, species-specific dispersal abilities cannot be explained by differences in body size but rather by differences in the ecological flexibility of the species.

3 Wissenschaftlicher Arbeits- und Ergebnisbericht/Scientific report

The processes leading to the diversification and distribution of species are of central interest for the discipline of evolutionary biology. We aimed to investigate the relative importance and interactions of various potential drivers of speciation within two exceptionally speciose lemur genera in Madagascar, *Lepilemur* (26 species) and *Microcebus* (24 species), in comparison to the less speciose but ecologically plastic genus *Avahi* (9 species). These taxa are to some extent co-distributed over northeastern Madagascar and offer highly suitable models to study the principal evolutionary processes driving species diversification in primates. Northeastern Madagascar is particularly suited for this purpose, because it is characterized by high- and lowland tropical rainforest vegetation on a steep east-west altitudinal

gradient and is traversed by 14 rivers of different sizes and ages. Thirteen study species (*Microcebus*: 7 species; *Lepilemur*: 4 species; *Avahi*: 2 species) were expected to occur in the region, each with distinct distributions.

Because field work could not take place as planned in the first year of the project due to a COVID-related closure of Madagascar's borders between 20.03.2020 – 06.11.2021, project progress was severely delayed and original research plans needed to be adapted. Specifically, we used the first year to address several relevant questions by using samples and data available from prior field work in adjacent geographic regions and from all over Madagascar, which we analyzed jointly together with other researchers within our mouse lemur consortium (see below). We resumed the planned fieldwork directly after the borders of Madagascar reopened. However, we encountered additional difficulties during our field work: Sampling *Lepilemur* spp. proved to be very difficult as they were only very rarely encountered even when specifically searching for them. In total, only five individual *Lepilemur* spp. could be captured, stemming from three inter-river-systems (IRSs), although 22 different sites were visited in 15 IRSs, and individuals of the two other lemur genera were captured with high success (captured *Microcebus* spp.: 286 individuals, captured *Avahi* spp.: 35 individuals, Figure 1B). Parallel interviews with local village communities revealed that illegal hunting on larger-bodied lemurs and very recent anthropogenic habitat loss and fragmentation are prominent in areas where we were not able to find *Lepilemur* spp. As a consequence, we only collected sufficient samples for the genera *Microcebus* and *Avahi* to conduct the planned phylogeographic, ecological and morphometric analyses but not for *Lepilemur*. In the rest of the report, we therefore talk on *Microcebus* spp. and *Avahi* spp.

The main goals of the original project were:

1. Elucidation of the role of river chronology and the size of rivers for the understanding of the biogeography and phylogeography of *Microcebus*, (*Lepilemur*) and *Avahi*.
2. Elucidation of the role of mountain ranges for the phylogeography of *Microcebus*, (*Lepilemur*) and *Avahi* species.
3. Evaluation of the relative importance of mountain ranges and of age and size of rivers for the diversification of small to medium-sized lemurs. For this evaluation, the results of aims 1) and 2) were integrated.
4. Evaluation of the relationship between species-specific connectivity and genetic diversity in *Microcebus*, (*Lepilemur*) and *Avahi*.
5. Evaluation of the occurrence and extent of admixture between mouse lemur species.
6. Evaluation of the relationship between ecological plasticity in lemurs and geographic range size.

Goal 1: The role of rivers

This task aimed at reconstructing river chronology and sizes in the study region and identifying to what extent they shaped the diversification and distribution of taxa. Because our parallel work revealed that mouse lemur diversification occurred very recently over the last 2 million years (van Elst et al. 2025a, below), and most river ages predate these events, we decided to focus on the effects of river size variation (Schüßler et al. 2025b). We included all 45 major rivers with headwater elevation of at least 700 m above sea level (a.s.l.) from the entire east coast of Madagascar, because this larger dataset allowed us to infer the effect of river size variation at higher resolution. For each river, we compiled 21 geomorphological river variables and reduced them to 11 uncorrelated variables for subsequent

modeling. To be able to generalize our results as much as possible across taxa, we assembled a database of distributions for 11 different genera including lemurs (*Eulemur*, *Haplemur*, *Lepilemur*, *Microcebus*, *Propithecus*, *Varecia*), amphibians (*Anodonthyla*, *Heterixalus*, *Mantella*) and reptiles (*Furcifer*, *Uroplatus*). Our inclusion criteria were that (a) the genus is widely distributed in eastern Madagascar, (b) the genus has at least two species, (c) the taxonomy is relatively settled, and (d) reliable distributional data were available with comprehensive IUCN assessments for verification purposes. These criteria led to the exclusion of *Avahi* for this partial study. We compared species occurrence data north and south of each river using the Jaccard dissimilarity index and detected that 24 rivers acted as species barriers for at least one species, with three major rivers having particularly high species turnover rates and acting as barriers for >11 species. Those rivers shared a set of distinct geomorphological features like a high maximum elevation of the watershed, high flow accumulation values at the outlet and at 800 m a.s.l., and a high concavity of the longitudinal river profile. Species richness peaked in northeastern Madagascar, a region with the highest abundance of topographic depressions and inferred palaeo-wetlands, which may have served as refugia during palaeoclimatic oscillations. Taken together, our study could show that integrating rivers as dynamic fluvial systems through space and time into biogeographic studies offers valuable insights into speciation events and connectivity. This study was prominently published very recently in the *Journal of Biogeography* (Schüßler et al. 2025b) and forms one chapter of the now completed PhD thesis of Dominik Schüßler. Two additional studies evaluated the role of rivers for the phylogeography of *Microcebus* spp. and *A. laniger* in the focal study region, but are detailed under Goal 3.

Goal 2: The role of mountain ranges

Elevation has been previously shown to constrain animal movement and thereby impact distributions of species. In our study we aimed to test (1) whether species-specific altitudinal plasticity explains differences in lemur distributions, (2) whether mountain ranges act as crossroads for species with high altitudinal plasticity, (3) whether introgression is higher in high-altitude sites than in low-altitude sites, and (4) whether larger lemurs have a higher altitudinal plasticity than smaller lemurs due to better thermoregulatory buffering given large body size. We could only recently address all of these questions, as we obtained the last genomic data for this partial project only in 2024.

The large-scale taxonomic confirmation that was recently achieved by the mouse lemur consortium and published prominently in van Elst et al. (2025a) revealed that the mouse lemur species with the highest altitudinal plasticity in eastern Madagascar, *Microcebus lehilahytsara* (25 – 1552 m a.s.l., Schüßler et al. 2025a), has indeed the largest distribution (Tiley et al. 2022). The very large altitudinal tolerance of this small-bodied mouse lemur demonstrated that there is no support for the hypothesis that larger bodied lemur species have larger distributions than smaller species. In addition, our results show that the larger *A. laniger* is not present on both sides of the Antainambalana River in the north of our study region and thereby may even have a more restricted overall distribution than *M. lehilahytsara* (van Elst et al. 2025b, Figure 1B).

Our genomic work has furthermore revealed that the north-south mountain range in eastern Madagascar indeed acted as crossroads for *M. lehilahytsara* that shows an isolation by distance pattern with clear signatures of highland-associated gene flow (Tiley et al. 2022, and Figure 2A). Congruently, most highland populations showed some level of admixture between the two principal genomic clusters that were detected (Figure 2A).

This pattern was not observed in *M. jonahi* which showed less altitudinal plasticity (9 – 953 m a.s.l., Schüßler et al. 2025a) and also more genetic structure (Figure 2B). Admixture between the two central

clusters within its range was detected inside IRS 9, and gene flow between sites existed but was strongest within IRSs and weaker between them (Figure 2B, van Elst et al. 2025b). Finally, the species with the lowest altitudinal plasticity (24 – 425 m a.s.l.), *M. macarthurii*, has the smallest geographic distribution, can be found in only one IRS (IRS5), and showed only marginal gene flow towards the neighboring *M. jonahi* (Figure 2B in dark blue). No genetic structure and high levels of gene flow were revealed for *A. laniger* despite its restricted range (Figure 2C). These genomic findings are currently assembled in a manuscript which was recently submitted for publication to *Molecular Ecology* (van Elst et al. 2025b).

Figure 2. Study region with pie charts illustrating the geographic representation of the genetic clusters revealed in independent ADMIXTURE analyses, and gene flow (direction and relative amount of gene flow is illustrated by arrows) inferred for *M. lehilahytsara* (A), *M. jonahi* (B), and *A. laniger* (C) (van Elst et al. 2025b)

Goal 3: The relative importance of mountains AND rivers for the diversification of small to medium-sized lemurs

The diversification of mouse lemurs was investigated from various perspectives and on various spatial scales, often in collaboration with other collaborators. The already mentioned mouse lemur consortium was formed in 2018 by researchers from the USA (Yoder-group), Portugal (Chikhi-group), France (Salmona-group) and Germany (Radespiel-group) to advance our understanding of mouse lemur evolution synergetically.

An early collaborative study, prominently pursued by my external doctoral student Dominik Schüßler with a focus on two understudied IRSs in northeastern Madagascar, led to the detection (Poelstra et al. 2020) and description of a new species of mouse lemurs, *M. jonahi* (Schüßler et al. 2020). Subsequently (still during COVID-times), we conducted another genomic single-species study with 67 already available DNA-samples collected over the entire range of *M. gerpi* (Radespiel et al., 2012), the southern neighbor of the group of mouse lemur species inhabiting northeastern Madagascar (Figure 1A). The range of *M. gerpi* shows remarkable similarities to northeastern Madagascar with several west-east flowing rivers cutting the distribution into six IRSs. We combined population genomic analyses, coalescent modelling, and ecological niche modelling to show that the phylogeographic history of this species can be largely explained by riverine barriers, altitude, and paleoclimatic oscillations (van Elst et al. 2023). More specifically, we found that *M. gerpi* populations form two highly genetically differentiated clades that occur on opposite sides of a large river system (Rianila/Vohitra) and diverged about 250 – 300 ka, potentially due to the disappearance of dispersal corridors across

high-altitude headwater regions during cool and arid climates in the late Pleistocene. Smaller rivers in the southern half of the distribution range also generated population structure, but lower levels of historic gene flow remained possible and divergence started only between 100–150 ka. Our findings support previous biogeographic models that explain the high levels of endemism in Madagascar through a combination of paleoclimatic oscillations, riverine barriers and altitude (e.g., the Eco-Geo-Clim model by Mercier & Wilmé 2013).

On a larger geographic and taxonomic scale, we also aimed to understand the diversification of the entire mouse lemur genus and this project was conducted as a core consortium activity and ended with its recent publication in *Nature Ecology and Evolution* with my doctoral student Tobias van Elst being the first author (van Elst et al. 2025a). In the course of this initiative, we developed best practices for detecting and describing cryptic diversification processes, and presented and tested an integrative new framework that leverages multiple lines of evidence and taxon-informed cut-offs for cryptic species delimitation, while taking into account patterns of isolation by distance whenever possible. We could show that mouse lemur species diversity has been overestimated (taxonomic inflation of 25 species, now reduced to 19, Figure 1A), mostly by wrongly interpreting geographic variation as speciation which led to biases in diversification estimates. Our analyses also revealed that cryptic species within this genus is best explained by a model of morphological stasis which seems imposed by stabilizing selection and by a neutral process of niche diversification. Finally, neighbouring and sister species were always isolated geographically, either by rivers or altitudinal gradients and no case of sympatric speciation or speciation by hybridization could be detected. Cases of sympatry can all be explained by one of two species (*M. murinus* and *M. lehilahytsara*) with a large distribution and high altitudinal plasticity co-occurring with a local or regional congener that lacks this level of plasticity. This new methodological framework and all associated genomic data and analytical scripts were deposited on GenBank and GitHub for future public use.

The analyses of the evolutionary origin of cryptic species in this genus became possible only because of a rigorous methodological pipeline that was developed for morphometric data cleaning and analysis in a parallel consortium study which was conducted mainly by my other doctoral student Dominik Schüßler, and published in parallel in the *American Journal of Biological Anthropology* (Schüßler et al. 2023). A total of 13 morphological variables were compiled for 3,073 individual mouse lemurs from 25 taxa and 153 different sampling localities, measured by 48 different field researchers. Our rigorous filtering pipeline reduced inter-observer bias considerably and thereby allowed us to evaluate sexual size dimorphism across the genus, and to test the applicability of three main biogeographic rules, the Rensch's rule, Allen's rule and Bergmann's rule, to mouse lemurs (Schüßler et al. 2023). Across species, mouse lemurs are sexually dimorphic (larger females), do not follow Rensch's rule for sexual size dimorphism or Bergmann's rule (as larger mouse lemur taxa live in warmer and wetter climates), but are concordant with Allen's rule, as shorter tails are associated with colder environments.

Goal 4: Relationship between species-specific connectivity and genetic diversity in *Microcebus*, (*Lepilemur*) and *Avahi*

Since a larger geographic distribution should be the result of a higher colonization potential and thereby higher vagility in space (Radespiel 2016), this trait should lead to a higher connectivity between subpopulations. In turn, species with a larger geographic distribution should have a higher genetic diversity in subpopulations of similar size than species with smaller geographic range. Mouse lemurs in northeastern Madagascar met this expectation. Both northern and southern populations of the widely distributed *M. lehilahytsara* showed significantly higher values of individual genomic

heterozygosity than any of the other species inhabiting smaller parts of the study region (Figure 3A, van Elst et al. 2025b). Notably, the species with the second largest distribution and intermediate levels of gene flow, *M. jonahi*, had intermediate levels of genetic diversity, while the species with the smallest distributions, *M. simmonsii* and *M. macarthurii*, showed the smallest genetic diversity.

In congruence with the high connectivity across its range, no geographic patterning was detected in the individual heterozygosities of *M. lehilahytsara*, and all values were relatively high with the exception of some outliers that had a relatively high proportion of missing data (Figure 3B). In the case of *M. jonahi*, however, genetic diversity declined gradually from north to south in congruence with a scenario of colonization from north to south and successive founder effects across the different involved IRS (Figure 3C). Intriguingly, the same geographic pattern was observed in *A. laniger* suggesting a similar phylogeographic history as *M. jonahi*, despite having much more overall connectivity and gene flow throughout (Figure 3D). The overall very high values of observed heterozygosity for *A. laniger* are remarkable, as local sightings were more frequent and effective population sizes were therefore likely also larger in the smaller *Microcebus* spp. than in medium-sized *A. laniger*. Possible explanations may lie in different dispersal abilities or in different demographic histories of the species.

Goal 5: Evaluation of the occurrence and extent of admixture between mouse lemur species to infer ancient or recent gene flow between sister lineages in adjacent IRSs

The only pair of sister species in the study region was *M. jonahi* - *M. macarthurii*. Previous work had already detected signals of mitochondrial introgression from *M. macarthurii* into *M. jonahi* (Radespiel et al. 2008, Poelstra et al. 2020). In our project, we could also infer low levels of gene flow between the two species (Figure 2B), which was also supported by a significant result for introgression and low levels of admixture at several *K* (van Elst et al. in prep.). How recent this signal is, remains to be explored. However, admixture was only detected with *M. jonahi* samples from the adjacent IRS6 suggesting that introgression between both species likely happened after or while *M. jonahi* colonized IRS6 and not before or during the initial divergence of both species in some zone of ancestral origin.

Figure 3A. Observed individual heterozygosity of *Microcebus* spp. in the study region. Colors code are used for different species. Estimates for *M. lehilahytsara* populations south of the region and the *M. murinus* outgroup (black) were added for comparison. Different bold letters on top indicate significance based on Dunn's tests ($p < 0.05$). Figure 3B/C/D. Observed heterozygosity of *M. lehilahytsara* (B), *M. jonahi*/*macarthurii* (C) and *Avahi* spp. (D) individuals in the study region plotted against latitude (South to North). Results of Spearman's rank correlation are given in the inlets. S: south; N: north.

Goal 6: Evaluation of the relationship between ecological plasticity in lemurs and geographic range size

We addressed this goal by investigating the use of different habitat types across a gradient of increasing anthropogenic disturbance that were differentially used by different mouse lemur species that differed in distribution, sympatry and altitudinal plasticity (Schüßler et al. 2025a). We distinguished between primary forest, selectively logged primary forest, highly logged primary forest, agroforestry, and fallow-derived regenerating vegetation following shifting cultivation (Savoka). We also determined four trait axes of niche differentiation (microhabitat structure, use of human-dominated landscapes, bioclimatic niche, morphological niche) for three mouse lemur species with sufficient data and determined the overlaps in their n-dimensional hypervolumes (Schüßler et al. 2025a) based on unequivocal sightings in allopatric populations and on captures (332 for *M. jonahi*, 62 for *M. lehilahytsara*, 73 for *M. simmonsii*). So far, the data have only been analyzed for mouse lemurs, and this manuscript is currently deposited on a public preprint server, while being submitted to and reviewed by a journal (chosen journal: *Biotropica*, Schüßler et al. 2025a). The ecological data for *Avahi* spp. will be analyzed later this year to also be published, although the dataset is much smaller (217 sightings and 35 captures). The analyses revealed that the widely distributed *M. lehilahytsara* used human-dominated landscapes more than its two congeners, but more frequently when in sympatry with one of the larger mouse lemur species than when forming allopatric populations. Congruently, this species also had the largest niche space of all mouse lemur species and in all four niche dimensions. These findings suggest that indeed the species with the largest geographic range and the highest altitudinal plasticity (*M. lehilahytsara*) showed the highest local habitat plasticity that probably allows this rather small mouse lemur to avoid competition in sympatry with its larger-bodied local and regional congeners (Schüßler et al. 2025a). Strong discordances between the climatic niche and the realized niche were shown for almost all mouse lemur species in our island-wide evaluation by van Elst et al. (2025a). These findings clearly underpin the barrier function of mountains and rivers for most mouse lemurs with the exception of *M. murinus* and *M. lehilahytsara* that maintain a high connectivity via highland areas within their respective distributions (van Elst et al. 2025a, Tiley et al. 2022, Poelstra et al. 2020, see above).

Access to research data: Datasets for all studies were deposited on public data repositories, i.e., GenBank (raw genomic data), Zenodo or GöttingenResearchOnline (processed data and results) and GitHub (scripts). Links are provided in the respective publications.

Communication of results: The results of this project were already presented through oral presentations at nine different conferences (1 national, 8 international) between 2022 and 2025.

Reference list (if not included under point 4): Mercier, J.-L., & Wilmé, L. (2013). The eco-geo-Clim model: Explaining Madagascar's endemism. *Mad. Cons. & Develop.*, **8**, 63–68. Radespiel, U. (2016). Can behavioral ecology help to understand the divergent geographic range sizes of mouse lemurs? Pp. 498–519 in: *The Dwarf and Mouse lemurs of Madagascar: Biology, Behavior and Conservation Biogeography of the Cheirogaleidae* (S. M. Lehman, U. Radespiel, and E. Zimmermann, eds.). Cambridge University Press. Cambridge, United Kingdom. Radespiel U., Olivieri G., Rasolofoson D.W., Rakotondratsimba G., Rakotonirainy O., Rasoloharijaona S., Randrianambinina B., Ratsimbazafy J.H., Ratelolahy F., Randriamboavonjy T., Rasolofoharivelo T., Craul M., Rakotozafy L., Randrianarison R.M. (2008). Exceptional diversity of mouse lemurs (*Microcebus* spp.) in the Makira region with the description of one new species. *Am. J. Primatol.*, **70**, 1033–1046.

4 Veröffentlichte Projektergebnisse/Published project results

4.1 Publikationen mit wissenschaftlicher Qualitätssicherung (publications with review system)

4.1.1 Core publications resulting from the DFG project (* in front: open access)

- *Schüßler D., Blanco M.B., Guthrie N.K., Sgarlata G.M., Dammhahn M., Refaly E., Rina Evasoa M., Hasiniaina A., Hending D., Jan F., le Pors B., Miller A., Olivieri G., Rakotonanahary A.N., Rakotondranary S.J., Rakotondravony R., Ralantoharijaona T., Ramananjato V., Randrianambinina B., Raelinjanakolona N.N., Rasoazanabary E., Rasoloarison R.M., Rasolofoson D.W., Rasoloharijaona S., Rasolondraibe E., Roberts S.H., Teixeira H., van Elst T., Johnson S.E., Ganzhorn J.U., Chikhi L., Kappeler P.M.; Louis Jr. E.E.; Salmona J.; Radespiel U. (2023): Morphological variability or inter-observer bias? A methodological toolkit to improve data quality of multi-researcher datasets for the analysis of morphological variation. *Am. J. of Biol. Anthropol.*, 183, 60-78. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajpa.24836>
- *Schüßler D.[#], Blanco M.B.[#], Salmona J., Poelstra J., Andriambelason J.B., Miller A., Randrianambinina B., Rasolofoson D.W., Mantilla-Contreras J., Chikhi L., Louis E.E. Jr., Yoder A.D., Radespiel, U. (2020): Ecology and morphology of mouse lemurs (*Microcebus* spp.) in a hotspot of microendemism in northeastern Madagascar, with the description of a new species. *Am. J. Primatol.*, 82, e23180. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajp.23180> (#: shared first authors)
- *Schüßler D., Bremer J., Sauerwein M., Radespiel, U. (2025b): Geomorphological river characteristics explain species turnover in amphibians, reptiles and lemurs in Madagascar's eastern rainforests. *J. Biogeogr.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.15109>
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4.1.2 Additional peer-reviewed publications that were enabled by the DFG-project

- *Rakotondravony R., Schüßler D., Rovanimirina V.S.R., Ratsimbazafy J., Radespiel U. (2023): Variation in abundance and habitat use of the Critically Endangered *Microcebus gerpi* across its fragmented range. *Am. J. Primatol.*, 85, e23553. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajp.23553>
- *Schüßler D., Mantilla-Contreras J., Stadtmann R., Ratsimbazafy J.H., Radespiel U. (2020): Identification of crucial stepping stone habitats for biodiversity conservation in northeastern Madagascar using remote sensing and comparative predictive modeling. *Biodiv. Conserv.*, 29, 2161-2184. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-020-01965-z>
- *Schüßler D., Rabemananjara N.R., Radriarimanga T., Rafamantanantsoa S.M., Randimbiharinarina R.D., Radespiel U., Hending D. (2023): Habitat and ecological niche characteristics of the elusive Hairy-eared Dwarf Lemur (*Allocebus trichotis*) with updated occurrence and geographic range data. *Am. J. Primatol.*, 85, e23473. <http://doi.org/10.1002/ajp.23473>
- *Schüßler D., Rafamantanantsoa S.M., Ratsimbazafy J.H., Richter T., Radespiel, U. (2024): Documentation of commercial and subsistence hunting of Critically Endangered Black-and-white Ruffed Lemurs (*Varecia variegata*) in northeastern Madagascar. *Biodiv. Conserv.*, 33, 221-237. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-023-02744-2>

4.2 Weitere Publikationen und öffentlich gemachte Ergebnisse/publications with no formal peer-review

- * Schüßler D., van Elst T., Rabemananjara N.R., Radriarimanga T., Rafamantanantsoa S.M., Randimbiharirina R.D., Rasolondraibe E., Mantilla-Contreras J., Radespiel U. (2025a): Ecological plasticity explains the distribution of sympatric and allopatric mouse lemurs (*Microcebus* spp.) in northeastern Madagascar. Preprint on BioRxiv. <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2025.03.24.645043v1>
- *Schüßler D., Rabemananjara N.R., Radriarimanga T., Rafamantanantsoa S.M., Randimbiharirina R.D., Radespiel U., Hending D. (2024): *Phaner furcifer* – The ghost lemur of northeastern Madagascar? *Lemur News*, 24, 19-23.
- * van Elst, T.; Schüßler, D.; Rafamantanantsoa, S.M.; Radriarimanga, T.; Rabemananjara, N.R.; Rasolofoson, E.W.; Randimbiharirina, R.D.; Hohenlohe, P.A.; Radespiel, U. (2025b). Species-specific responses to paleoclimatic changes and landscape barriers drive contrasting phylogeography of co-distributed lemur species in northeastern Madagascar. Preprint available at BioRxiv <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.06.11.658897>

4.3 Patente (angemeldete und erteilte)

Not relevant.